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World Inventory of Beetles of the Family *Bostrichidae* (Coleoptera). Part 1. Check List from 1758 to 2012

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents list of beetles of the family Bostrichidae and their occurrence. The paper includes: 7 subfamilies, 4 tribes, 28 genera, 5 subgenera and 155 species of beetles belonging to the family Bostrichidae.

Keywords: Dinoderinae, Dysidinae, Endecatominae, Euderinae, Lyctinae, Polycaoninae, Psoinae

Subfamilies

<i>Dinoderinae</i>156
<i>Dysidinae</i>160
<i>Endecatominae</i>160
<i>Euderiinae</i>160
<i>Lyctinae</i>161
<i>Polycaoninae</i>165
<i>Psoinae</i>167

– Check List –

Kingdom: *Animalia*

Phylum: *Arthropoda*

Class: *Hexapoda*

Order: *Coleoptera*

Family *Bostrichidae* Latreille, 1802

Subfamily *Dinoderinae* C.G. Thomson, 1863

Genus *Dinoderus* Stephens, 1830

Subgenus *Dinoderus* s. str.

Dinoderus (Dinoderus) bifoveolatus (Wollaston, 1858)

Distribution: Cosmopolitan

Dinoderus (Dinoderus) borneanus Lesne, 1933

Distribution: Borneo

Dinoderus (Dinoderus) brevis Horn, 1878

Distribution: Oriental and Australian Regions

Dinoderus (Dinoderus) creberrimus Lesne, 1941

Distribution: India

Dinoderus (Dinoderus) distinctus Lesne, 1897

Distribution: Philippines

Dinoderus (Dinoderus) favosus Lesne, 1911

Distribution: Vietnam, Thailand, Andamans

Dinoderus (Dinoderus) gabonicus Lesne, 1921

Distribution: West Africa

Dinoderus (Dinoderus) gardneri Lesne, 1933

Distribution: India

Dinoderus (Dinoderus) glabripennis Lesne, 1911

Distribution: Burma

Dinoderus (Dinoderus) mangiferae Lesne, 1921

Distribution: India

Dinoderus (Dinoderus) minutus (Fabricius, 1775)

Distribution: Cosmopolitan

Dinoderus (Dinoderus) nitidus Lesne, 1897

Distribution: New Guinea, Marquesas Islands

Dinoderus (Dinoderus) oblongopunctatus Lesne, 1923

Distribution: Africa

Dinoderus (Dinoderus) ocellaris Stephens, 1830

Distribution: Cosmopolitan species, most common in the Oriental Region

Dinoderus (Dinoderus) ochraceipennis Lesne, 1906

Distribution: Indochinese Peninsula

Dinoderus (Dinoderus) papuanus Lesne, 1899

Distribution: New Guinea, Australia

Dinoderus (Dinoderus) perfoliatus Gorham, 1886

Distribution: Central America

Dinoderus (Dinoderus) perplexus Lesne, 1932

Distribution: India

Dinoderus (Dinoderus) piceolus Lesne, 1933

Distribution: China (Hong Kong)

Dinoderus (Dinoderus) politulus Lesne, 1941

Distribution: Southern India

Dinoderus (Dinoderus) porcellus Lesne, 1923

Distribution: West Africa

Dinoderus (Dinoderus) punctatissimus Lesne 1897

Distribution: India

Subgenus *Dinoderastes* Lesne, 1914

Dinoderus (Dinoderastes) exilis Lesne, 1932

Distribution: India (Assam)

Dinoderus (Dinoderastes) japonicus Lesne, 1895

Distribution: Japan, China, Taiwan

Dinoderus (Dinoderastes) scabricauda Lesne, 1914

Distribution: Philippines

Dinoderus (Dinoderastes) speculifer Lesne, 1895

Distribution: China, Taiwan, Japan

Genus ***Prostephanus*** Lesne, 1897

Subgenus ***Prostephanus*** s. str.

Prostephanus (Prostephanus) apax Lesne 1930

Distribution: USA (Arizona), Central America

Prostephanus (Prostephanus) arizonicus Fisher, 1950

Distribution: USA (Arizona)

Prostephanus (Prostephanus) punctatus (Say, 1826)

Distribution: Eastern states of USA

Prostephanus (Prostephanus) sulcicollis (Fairmaire et Germain, 1861)

Distribution: Chile

Prostephanus (Prostephanus) truncatus (Horn, 1878)

Distributions: USA, Central America, introduced to nearly all continents

Subgenus ***Dinoderopsis*** Lesne, 1906

Prostephanus (Dinoderopsis) escharipora (Lesne, 1906)

Distribution: Yemen (Socotra)

Prostephanus (Dinoderopsis) opimus (Lesne, 1938)

Distribution: South Africa

Prostephanus (Dinoderopsis) serriger (Lesne, 1923)

Distribution: East and South Africa

Subgenus ***Orientoderus*** Borowski et Węgrzynowicz, 2011

Prostephanus (Orientoderus) orientalis Borowski et Węgrzynowicz, 2011

Distribution: Northern Laos, Thailand

Genus *Rhizoperthodes* Lesne, 1936

Rhizoperthodes anguinus Lesne, 1936
Distribution: Malaysia

Genus *Rhyzopertha* Stephens, 1830

Rhyzopertha dominica (Fabricius, 1792)
Distribution: Cosmopolitan

Genus *Stephanopachys* Waterhouse, 1888

Stephanopachys amplus (Casey, 1898)
Distribution: USA (Arizona, Michigan)

Stephanopachys asperulus (Casey, 1898)
Distribution: USA (Arizona, New Mexico)

Stephanopachys brunneus (Wollaston, 1862)
Distribution: Canary Islands

Stephanopachys conicola Fisher, 1950
Distribution: USA (Arizona, California)

Stephanopachys cribratus (LeConte, 1866)
Distribution: North America

Stephanopachys densus (LeConte, 1866)
Distribution: North America

Stephanopachys dugesi Lesne, 1939
Distribution: Mexico

Stephanopachys himalayanus Lesne, 1932
Distribution: Himalaya

Stephanopachys hispidulus (Casey, 1898)
Distribution: Eastern states of USA

Stephanopachys linearis (Kugelann, 1792)
Distribution: Europe, North Asia

Stephanopachys quadricollis (Fairmaire in Marseul, 1878)
Distribution: Mediterranean area

Stephanopachys rugosus (Olivier, 1795)

Distribution: Eastern states of USA

Stephanopachys sobrinus (Casey, 1898)

Distribution: North America

Stephanopachys substriatus (Paykull, 1800)

Distribution: Europe, Norther Asia, North America

Subfamily ***Dysidinae*** Lesne, 1921

Genus ***Apoleon*** Gorham, 1885

Apoleon edax Gorham, 1885

Distribution: Indochnese Peninsula, Malaysia, Indonesia

Genus ***Dysides*** Perty, 1832

Dysides obscurus Perty, 1832

Distribution: South America

Subfamily ***Endecatominiae*** LeConte, 1861

Genus ***Endecatomus*** Mellie, 1847

Endecatomus dorsalis Mellie, 1848

Distribution: Southern and central states of USA

Endecatomus lanatus (Lesne, 1934)

Distribution: East Siberia China, Japan

Endecatomus reticulatus (Herbst, 1793)

Distribution: Southern and Central Europe

Endecatomus rugosus (Randall, 1938)

Distribution: Central and eastern states of USA

Subfamily ***Euderiinae*** Lesne, 1934

Genus ***Euderia*** Broun, 1880

Euderia squamosa Broun, 1880

Distribution: New Zealand

Subfamily *Lyctinae* Billberg, 1820

Tribe *Lyctini* Billberg, 1820

Genus *Acantholyctus* Lesne, 1924

Acantholyctus cornifrons (Lesne, 1898)

Distribution: Africa and southern part of Arabian Peninsula

Genus *Lyctoplites* Lesne, 1935

Lyctoplites armatus Lesne, 1935

Distribution: West Africa

Genus *Lyctodon* Lesne 1937

Lyctodon bostrychoides Lesne 1937

Distribution: Australia

Genus *Lyctoxylon* Reitter, 1879

Lyctoxylon beesonianum Lesne, 1936

Distribution: Northern India

Lyctoxylon convictor Lesne, 1936

Distribution: Northern and Western India

Lyctoxylon dentatum (Pascoe, 1866)

Distribution: Indian and Indochinese Peninsula

Genus *Lyctus* Fabricius, 1792

Lyctus africanus Lesne, 1907

Distribution: Africa, Arabian Peninsula

Lyctus brunneus (Stephens, 1830)

Distribution: Cosmopolitan, but preferring areas of tropical and subtropical, as well as marine temperate climate

Lyctus carbonarius Waltl, 1832

Distribution: USA, Mexico

Lyctus caribeus Lesne, 1931

Distribution: Central America, USA (introduced)

Lyctus cavicollis LeConte, 1866

Distribution: USA, Mexico, Australia (introduced), Europe (introduced)

Lyctus chacoensis Santoro, 1960

Distribution: Argentina

Lyctus cinereus Blanchard, 1851

Distribution: South America

Lyctus discedens Blackburn, 1888

Distribution: India, Sri Lanka, Indochinese Peninsula, Malaysia, Indonesia, New Guinea, Australia, New Zealand and Europe (introduced)

Lyctus hipposideros Lesne, 1908

Distribution: Africa, Europe (Finland, Switzerland, Italy) (introduced)

Lyctus kosciuszko Borowski & Wegrzynowicz, 2007

Distribution: USA (Southwestern states)

Lyctus linearis (Goeze, 1777)

Distribution: Holarctic species, Argentina (introduced), Australia (introduced)

Lyctus longicornis Reitter, 1879

Distribution: Colombia

Lyctus opaculus LeConte, 1866

Distribution: Canada, Northeastern and Central States of USA

Lyctus parallelocollis Blackburn, 1888

Distribution: Australia, New Guinea, Israel (introduced)

Lyctus pubescens Panzer, 1793

Distribution: Palaearctic species. Introduced to Australia, New Zealand, New Guinea

Lyctus simplex Reitter, 1879

Distribution: South America, Europe (Sweden, Germany) and RSA (introduced)

Lyctus sinensis Lesne, 1911

Distribution: China, Japan, Australia (introduced), Europe (Great Britain), New Guinea, New Zealand (introduced)

Lyctus suturalis Faldermann, 1837

Distribution: Caucasus, South Kazakhstan, Turkmenistan, Tajikistan, Uzbekistan

Lyctus tomentosus Reitter, 1879

Distribution: Central America, USA (including Hawaii) and Thailand (introduced)

Lyctus turkestanicus Lesne, 1935

Distribution: China, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan, Tajikistan

Lyctus villosus Lesne, 1911

Distribution: Central America, Greater Antilles, USA (introduced)

Genus ***Minthea*** Pascoe, 1866

Minthea acanthacollis (Carter et Zeck, 1937)

Distribution: Australia

Minthea bivestita Lesne, 1937

Distribution: Indochinese Peninsula

Minthea humericosta Lesne, 1936

Distribution: New Guinea and Oceania

Minthea obsita (Wollaston, 1867)

Distribution: Africa South of Sahara, Madagascar, Introduced to almost all continents

Minthea reticulata Lesne, 1931

Distribution: Indochinese Peninsula, Taiwan, Indonesia, New Guinea, Oceania, Introduced to Europe and USA

Minthea rugicollis (Walker, 1858)

Distribution: Cosmopolitan species of Asiatic origin

Minthea squamigera Pascoe, 1866

Distribution: South America. Introduced to Central and North America and to Europe

Tribe ***Trogoxylini*** Lesne, 1921

Genus ***Cephalotoma*** Lesne, 1911

Cephalotoma africanum (Grouvelle, 1900)

Distribution: West Africa

Cephalotoma ambiguum (Lesne, 1936)

Distribution: India

Cephalotoma coomani (Lesne, 1932)

Distribution: Indochinese Peninsula

Cephalotoma perdepressa Lesne, 1937

Distribution: Vietnam

Cephalotoma singularis Lesne, 1911

Distribution: Indochinese Peninsula, Indonesia, New Guinea

Cephalotoma testaceum (Lesne, 1913)

Distribution: Tropical Africa

Genus *Lyctopsis* Lesne, 1911

Lyctopsis inquilina Lesne, 1932

Distribution: South-East Africa

Lyctopsis pachymera Lesne, 1911

Distribution: Central Africa

Lyctopsis scabricollis Lesne, 1911

Distribution: East Africa, Arabian Peninsula

Genus *Phyllyctus* Lesne, 1911

Phyllyctus gounellei (Grouvelle, 1896)

Distribution: South America

Genus *Tristaria* Reitter, 1878

Tristaria grouvellei Reitter, 1878

Distribution: Australia

Genus *Trogoxylon* LeConte, 1862

Trogoxylon aequale (Wollaston, 1867)

Distribution: Southern states of USA, Central America. Introduced to various countries throughout the world

Trogoxylon angulicollis Santoro, 1960

Distribution: Argentina

Trogoxylon auriculatum Lesne, 1932

Distribution: Indochinese Peninsula

Trogoxylon caseyi Lesne, 1937

Distribution: USA (Texas)

Trogoxylon giacobbii Santoro, 1957

Distribution: Brazil, Paraguay, Argentina

Trogoxylon impressum (Comolli, 1837)

Distribution: South Europe, North Africa, Asia Minor, Turkmenistan, USA (introduced), Argentina (introduced) RSA (introduced), Australia (introduced)

Trogoxylon parallelipedum (Melsheimer, 1846)

Distribution: Southern and Central states of USA, Australia (introduced), Europe (introduced)

Trogoxylon praeustum (Erichson, 1847)

Distribution: Southwestern states of USA, Central America, South America (introduced) Philippines, (introduced), Europe (introduced)

Trogoxylon punctatum LeConte, 1866

Distribution: Southwestern states of USA, Mexico

Trogoxylon punctipenne (Fauvel, 1904)

Distribution: India, Indochinese Peninsula, New Guinea, New Caledonia, Australia

Trogoxylon rectangulum Lesne, 1921

Distribution: Dominican Republic

Trogoxylon retille Reitter, 1879

Distribution: Argentina

Trogoxylon spinifrons (Lesne, 1910)

Distribution: India, Indochinese Peninsula, New Guinea

Trogoxylon ypsilon Lesne, 1937

Distribution: Australia, Tasmania, New Guinea

Subfamily ***Polycaoninae*** Lesne, 1896

Genus ***Melalgus*** Dejean, 1833

Melalgus amoenus (Lesne, 1911)

Distribution: Mexico

Melalgus batillus (Lesne, 1902)

Distribution: Vietnam, India, China

Melalgus borneensis (Lesne, 1911)

Distribution: Malaysia (Sabah, Perak)

Melalgus caribeanus (Lesne, 1906)

Distribution: Greater and Lesser Antilles

Melalgus confertus (LeConte, 1866)

Distribution: USA (California, Oregon)

Melalgus crassulus (Lesne, 1911)

Distribution: Mexico

Melalgus digueti (Lesne, 1911)

Distribution: Mexico

Melalgus exesus (LeConte, 1858)

Distribution: USA (Texas), Mexico, Honduras, Panama

Melalgus feanus (Lesne 1899)

Distribution: India, Vietnam, China, Burma, Thailand

Melalgus femoralis (Fabricius, 1792)

Distribution: Great Antilles, Lesser Antilles, French Guiana

Melalgus gracilipes (Blanchard, 1843)

Distribution: Brazil, Bolivia, Argentina

Melalgus jamaicensis (Lesne, 1906)

Distribution: Jamaica, Bahamas, Caymans

Melalgus longitarsus (Lesne, 1911)

Distribution: Mexico

Melalgus megalops (Fall, 1901)

Distribution: USA (California)

Melalgus parvidens (Lesne, 1895)

Distribution: Brazil

Melalgus parvulus (Lesne, 1925)

Distribution: Mexico

Melalgus plicatus (LeConte, 1874)

Distribution: USA (Texas, Georgia), Mexico

Melalgus rufipes (Blanchard, 1843)
Distribution: Bolivia, Paraguay, Argentina

Melalgus strigipennis (Lesne, 1937)
Distribution: Mexico, Colombia, Brazil

Melalgus subdepressus (Lesne, 1897)
Distribution: Mexico

Melalgus truncatus (Guerin-Meneville, 1844)
Distribution: French Guiana, Venezuela

Melalgus valleculatus (Lesne, 1913)
Distribution: Argentina

Genus *Polycaon* Castelnau, 1836

Polycaon chilensis (Erichson, 1834)
Distribution: Brazil, Peru, Bolivia, Chile

Polycaon granulatus Van Dyke, 1923
Distribution: USA (California)

Polycaon punctatus LeConte, 1866
Distribution: USA (California)

Polycaon stoutii (LeConte, 1853)
Distribution: Southern and western states of USA, Mexico

Subfamily *Psoinae* Blanchard, 1851

Tribe *Chileniini* Lesne, 1921

Genus *Chilenius* Lesne, 1921

Chilenius spinicollis (Fairmaire et Germain, 1861)
Distribution: Chile

Chilenius tabulifrons Lesne, 1935
Distribution: Chile

Tribe *Psoini* Blanchard, 1851

Genus *Coccographis* Lesne, 1901

Coccographis nigrorubra Lesne, 1901

Distribution: Indochinese Peninsula

Genus *Heteropsoa* Lesne, 1895

Heteropsoa australis Lesne, 1895

Distribution: South Africa

Heteropsoa macrops Lesne, 1938

Distribution: South Africa

Genus *Psoa* Herbst, 1797

Psoa dubia (Rossi, 1792)

Distribution: Southern Europe, Asia Minor, North Africa

Psoa maculata (LeConte, 1852)

Distribution: USA (California)

Psoa quadrisignata (Horn, 1868)

Distribution: Western states of USA

Psoa viennensis Herbst, 1797

Distribution: South and southern part of Central Europe, Caucasus, Asia Minor

Genus *Psoidia* Lesne, 1912

Psoidia pexicollis Lesne, 1912

Distribution: South India

Genus *Stenomera* Lucas, 1850

Stenomera assyria Lesne, 1895

Distribution: Turkey, Syria, Iraq, Iran

Stenomera blanchardii Lucas, 1850

Distribution: Morocco, Algeria, Tunisia

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